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***Okwurukwusike* Traditional Dance Group Of Isuofia In Aguata Local Government Area Of Anambra State: A Documentation For Future Generational Transfer**

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ABSTRACT

The work centers on the documentation and archiving of *Okwurukwusike* Traditional dance Group through modern Technological devices that can record and preserve such dance in the music studios, museums, CDs, discs, libraries and/or academic institutions and music departmental libraries for future use and generational transfer. *Okwurukwusike* traditional dance is exclusively performed by the women of Umueze village of Isuofia town and it needs to be recorded, documented and archived for generational transfer to prevent it from total extinction. Therefore, this research presents a brief study on the historical background of Isuofia community, brief history of their songs, the instruments, performance occasions and costumes of the dance group. The work hinges on cultural and socialization theories. The researchers applied the use of direct contact, face-to-face interviews, participant observation, library and internet (assets) as the methods of data collection. The music of *Okwurukwusike* gives one a sense of belonging especially among the women folk during their outing and performances. It also exposes the integrity of the women folk in cultural, social, economic, physical, historical and therapeutic healing. Based on these, recommendations were made pertinent among which is encouraging their married women in other villages of Isuofia; Ozalla, Isiaku, Ezioka, Okpoko and Akuru to learn such expedient music.

Keywords: *Okwurukwusike* Traditional dance Group, women

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, almost every society has its music traditions which the people use in preserving, documenting and archiving ethical values, and such is found in Igbo community of Nigerian society because music occupies a vital place in their daily events. Odogbor (2008) asserted that,

music occupies a vital place in the life of every Nigerian. Its importance informs its integration into the day-to-day activities of any traditional community. Even in the contemporary Nigerian society, music functions one form or another in the life of an individual, groups, or the entire society. Traditional music, especially, assumes a central role in the light of the fact that it has continued to be used as a carrier of the people's history and tradition, in the inculcation of cultural values (p. 67).

Similarly, Idolor (2002) posited that, "no phenomenon void of utility survives in a society, an indication that the preserving of music in almost every African society has a formidable role to fulfill" (p. 2). In the light of the above, *Okwurukwusike* Traditional Dance Group of Isuofia is a meaningful dance that helps its community in making their cultural events attractive and lively. Agu (2017) submitted that, "A people's music portrays who they are, where they come from and their values" (p. 6). So, it is with *Okwurukwusike* Traditional Dance Group of Isuofia as they value and appreciate music in their day-to-day activities. Ekong (2008) ascertained that, "music is what gives a society life and cultural identity; just as culture defies specific traditions, so is music" (p. 17). Such is found in the music of *Okwurukwusike* Traditional Dance Group because they carry and disseminate the community's customs and traditions, through practical means. Omibiyi-Obidike in Ezeugwu (2015) posited that, "music is a language, a social communicator, a messenger in peace and war, an educator, a phenomenon that is integral in all aspects of our culture and therefore must be produced through practical process" (p. 110). From the above submission, it shows that there is need for the documentation and archiving of this very important indigenous music that carries the traditions, customs, ethics, pathos, ethos and values of the up-coming generations.

However, most musical and/or dance groups such as *Okwurukwusike* Traditional Dance Group can no longer attract and encourage new and young women members for the continuity of the dance group. As such, there is need for the documentation of

Okwurukwusike dance group to avoid it from phasing out completely. More so, the newly married ones join their husbands to the urban cities in search of greener pasture because most of the women that are presently in the dance group are from 45-75 years old. Nonetheless, the music has not been recorded for reference purposes.

Theoretical Framework

The work hinges on socialization and cultural theories. The two (2) theories were differently and collectively explained, as they relate to the study.

Socialization Theory

The theory of socialization was propounded and developed by Charles Horton, Cooley George Herbert Mead and Sigmund Freud. The theorists clarify that a person or human being acquires the skills necessary to perform as functional members of his or her society, thereby learning all about his/her culture and its environment, to be able to live within its required principles and demands. Ahamefula and Ejiogu (2014) stated that,

Socialization is how human infants begin to acquire the skills necessary to perform as functioning members of their society, and it is the most influential learning process one can experience. Unlike other living species, whose behavior is biologically set, humans need social experiences to learn and to survive (p. 51).

As such, members of *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group acquire musical skills through their dance performances thereby relating with one another and learning about their societal behaviour as well as their culture which the music carries.

In addition, through the dance performance and musical activities of *Okwurukwusike*, they learn about the required and desirable functions, customs, traditions, norms, morals, values and group associations to fit-in and relate effectively and efficiently in the community where they belong. The community on its own part, benefits directly and indirectly from the musical/dance group through mutual and cordial understanding of individual differences as well as respecting one another. The group through its dance or music further learns to tolerate and get along with people within and outside the group. Thus, man as a social animal needs to learn what is obtainable in the environment where he lives.

However, the way people socialize in the environment where they live affect their general way of life which *Okwurukwusike* dance group inculcates. Uzoma and Ike (2019) inferred that, "Among traditional African communities, music making is closely related with and recognized as a social activity that fosters and reinforces communal unity" (p. 197). The above statement clarifies the statement of socialization theory as a means by which a person acquires the skills to perform as a formidable member of his community for cordial unity, co-operation and development.

Cultural Theory

The cultural theory states that culture shapes and is shaped by human experience, social structures, and power relationships. The propounders of this theory were Douglas and Wildavsky. Since culture shapes human experience and human experiences is in turn shaped by culture, *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group therefore, carries, inculcates and initiates the cultural values of its community such as their customs, taboos, traditions, ethics and general way of life of its people to ensure harmonious living. Likewise, the culture of the community inculcates and directs the affairs of *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group to suit the community which is transferred from generation to generation. Peters in International Encyclopedia (2001) stated that, "cultural theories regard education as an initiation and are justified in a transcendental manner" (p. 1) (internet asset). In the light of the above statement, *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group is highly educative in shaping the character of the community through its performances. While the cultural values of the communities which the dance group carries, directs the dance group behaviour to fit the socio-cultural demands of the community, to help the up-coming generations for progressive and smooth continuity of their general welfare. Hence, cultural theory here portrays that *Okwurukwusike*, through its initiative experiences with the performances, inculcates the required behaviour in the society, as the society also shapes the character of the dance group to fit properly with the community's wish and this is transferred from generation to generation for the community's cordial growth and development. Ume and Ajiwe (2023) ascertained that, "Traditional African dances have symbolic signs inherent in the dances; as such, these signs form the ideas communicated through the dance and portray the cultural value of the community" (p. 13). The above statement clarifies community's dance as a carrier and initiator of the people's cultural values. Yekini-Ajenifuja (2011) affirmed that, "music in Africa portrays the totality of its cultural product. It cannot be separated from culture, because in culture there is music and in music there is culture" (p. 69). This is so because music is used in preserving, documenting, sustaining, archiving and transforming the culture of its people.

METHODOLOGY

Data for the work were gathered from different sources. These include interviews from five (5) people – three (3) women participants, and two (2) men for the brief historical background of the town. The interview took place in their residents, dance arena and rehearsal compounds respectively which is shown in the body of the work. There is also participant observation, and direct contact with custodians of the tradition and customs as well as internet and libraries. The respondents were practically observed and interviewed both individually and collectively by the researchers during their rehearsals, social functions and outing ceremonies in their village squares, host's residents and event centres for accurate and first-hand information.

Consequently, after the researchers had been acquainted with the necessary materials for the work, the researchers made several visits to the resource persons to negotiate and familiarize with them, and fix dates for the actual work. Three sets of interview-schedules were constructed for the respondents: the history of *Okwurukwusike*, the importance, the songs, the instruments, the process of archiving and generational transfer of the dance. From the practical interviews and participant's observations relevant to the study, the data were based on first-hand information and account from the performers of *Okwurukwusike* dance, the

custodians of Isuofia community history/tradition, who has the raw materials of the study. For the participants of *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group, three women were interviewed, and the questions were framed to obtain as much information as possible, following: The first interview was held on 5th April 2024 with a 70 year old member of the dance group, Roselyn Ezeanya from Ozalla village in her residence.

The second interview was held on 11th May 2024 with 65 years old member, Chinyere Onuforom from Umueze in her business centre.

The third interview was held on 7th June 2024 with 45 years old member, Ebere Udensi from Umueze in her residence.

Clarification of Terms

Some of the words that needs clarification with reference to the study are explained as follows.

Okwurukwusike

The word *Okwurukwusike* is an Igbo vernacular word meaning to be firm or maintaining one's stand, no matter the situation. It also means that a person's affirmation should either be yes or no, to maintain one's integrity, dignity and decency in our dealings. When this word name is related to the dance group, it means that the dance is known for the group's integrity, truthfulness fairness and firmness in character and in performance. As such, it is pertinent to be recorded and documented for future use.

Traditional Dance Group

A traditional dance group is an indigenous dance troupe of a particular community which carries the performing actions among the symbolic signs that are inherent in the dances and portrayed as required by the society that owns it. Traditional dance-members of an indigenous community which occur within the socio-cultural settings of the ethics, traditions, customs, institutions and life observances, which are peculiar to the individual or group of a Nigerian society. Traditional dance group is a rhythmic bodily performance actions/gestures of a group with symbolic elements such as music, instruments, aesthetic body paintings with decorative designs, costumes and/or regalia that portray meaningful expositions to entertain the audience.

Therefore, traditional dance group is a set of performing cultural dance organization of a people or rural area which carries the signs and symbols of its community to convey, communicate and transfer a message as well as entertain the audience. Ume and Ajiwe (2023) ascertained that "traditional dances in Nigeria are often laden with signs and symbols that represent the idea and purpose of dance as well as community that originated the dance" (p.19). Nevertheless, *Okwurukwusike* is a traditional dance group that contain a unique purpose that needs to be documented, archived and transferred to their future generations for its continuity. Ntorem (2019) posited that, "African traditional dance are the indigenous dances of communities in Africa, and these dances are accompanied by traditional music. Some of the culture and norms of these communities are showcased in their music and dance" (p. 308). So, it is with *Okwurukwusike* traditional dance. Hence, the need for the study.

Documentation and Archiving

Documentation is the process of observing, recording and preserving an important item for future reference purposes.

Nwankpa (2020) inferred that,

By documentation, we refer to the process of preserving information, objects, tangible and intangible materials of cultural heritage, events and so on for posterity. The techniques and strategies of documentation are varied and these will include print and electronic methods of preservation, and oral tradition or documentation (p. 4).

The above statement showcases that important information for cultural heritage and posterity should be preserved through documentation which may be oral or written.

Archiving is the process of collecting and storing information to be retrieved for usage when there is need. Nwankpa (2020) observed that.

Archiving can be defined as the method and strategy of keeping these records, files, documents and collection of historical, socio-political, educational report on various ethnic groups, for presentation and for easy reference.

The place where these historical materials and important items of information are housed may be in a building designed as an archive or in a library or centre. Furthermore, archiving is the process of managing, developing, preserving, and storing valuable records of a people, place, organization, institution or government.

The documents and materials can be tangible or intangible material of the culture of the people. Archiving is, therefore, the way of putting away for safe keeping documents or information not often needed. Consequently, an archive is a place where important historical documents and records are stored (p. 5).

Therefore, documentation and archiving are two words that move together to achieve proper preservation and retrieval of salient information for effective and efficient generational use and progressive transfer to the up-coming generations. Onyenye (2020) affirm that, "archiving means the process of recording related activities of communities and other phenomena of society. This definition is applicable to archiving and documentation of information with cultural background" (p. 209).

Generational Transfer

Generational transfer is the art and act of transferring an important information that may be tangible or intangible to the up-coming generations. It can also be defined as a process of handing over effective and efficient record of materials for reference purposes to the future generations. It is the keeping and transmission of cultural valued messages and knowledge for up-coming children and youths for community's continuity of indigenous traditions through traditional music like *Okwurukwusike* Traditional Dance Group. Adetunji (2023) asserted that, "music plays a significant role in preserving and promoting cultural values, traditions, and beliefs in Nigeria. It serves as a mirror of cultural identities, facilitates the transmission of cultural knowledge, and promotes unity and integration among communities (p. 115). Nevertheless, *Okwurukwusike* is a diligent platform to be used in recording, documenting, archiving, preserving and transmitting cultural values from one generation to another to ensure continuity.

Brief Historical Background of Isuofia Community in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State

From direct contact with the owners and custodians of Isuofia tradition, Sunday Osele stated that Isuofia people migrated from different places like Isuochi, Amaetiti and Isunjaba. In collaboration to the above, Mazi Fidelis Okafor also stated that a migrant who came on hunting expedition from Isulo married and got two sons – Amafor and Amankwo. The sons, Amafor and Amankwo grew up strong, became powerful hunters, animal rearers and subsistence farmers. They subsequently married and got their own children as well.

More so, the respondents collaborated by stating that Isuofia is made up of six (6) villages namely: Umueze, Ozara, Isiaku, Ezioka, Okpoko and Akuru.

(Sunday Osele, Saturday, 4th May 2024; 8.00am – 10.30am, Umueze village Isuofia and Fidelis Okafor, Friday 7th June 2024; 2.00pm – 3.45pm, Ezioka village, Isuofia ; Oral Communication).

Location

Isuofia is one of the major towns in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State. Approximately, it is located between longitudes 5^o46’ 24” and 6^o45’ 07” East of the Greenwich Meridian, as well as Latitudes 5^o40’ 18” and 6^o45’ 13” North of the Equator. Relatively, the state has common boundaries with River Niger, on the East, Imo State on the South, Enugu State on the West and Benue on the North (Wikipedia).

Map Anambra State

As regards their economic life, Isuofia people are businessmen and women residing in different locations of Nigeria where they work fervently to earn their living. They also train their children to be hardworking in diverse areas of life endeavours like farming and trading in different kinds of items. Isuofia community is known for subsistent farming. They produce staple foods like yam, cassava, mazie etc. In the area of religion, they were known for African Traditional Religion (ATR) before the advent of Christianity. Today, they are mainly Christians with some traces of traditional worshipping. Socio-culturally, Isuofia people engage in social and cultural activities that involve traditional music such as ... marriage, burial, new yam and birthday celebrations. As a matter of fact, music performances reveal much about a people’s way of life. Music also goes beyond entertainment purposes. It expresses emotions, moods, ideas, tell stories, serves religious, political, cultural and social needs. Music making is simply an experience that is pleasurable, exciting and aesthetically valuable.

Feelings and ideas can be expressed and communicated, sharing rhythm and movement can make people unified. Such is what is portrayed by *Okwurukwusike* Traditional Dance Group of Isuofia. Nwauzor (2012) observed that, “when music and dance is being performed, it heightens the standard and level of awareness in the socio-cultural belief of the society” (p.195).

In the light of the above statement, it portrays that music and dance are deeply interwoven into the socio-cultural fabric on many Nigerian societies of which Isuofia is a part. Lo-Banujoko (1984) opined that, “every community must continue to sustain its musical culture as a stabilizing force” (p.40). Besides, in the above view, music and dance serve as a major art and essential element in the celebration of life events or occasions such as: childbirth celebrations, initiation ceremonies, title taking, burial, traditional marriage and other ceremonial occasions. Such occasion attracts the music of *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group of Isuofia.

Brief Historical Background of Okwurukwusike Dance Group

Okwurukwusike Dance Group is a dignified women dance group from Isuofia. The group is blessed with almost all the structural qualities of African dance formation. It is an embodiment of form, movement variations as well as creating room for free medley and stylized demonstrations at different sections of the dance. From a direct source of face-to-face interview, Roselyn Ezeanya (2024) states that, *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group is a well-known dance in Isuofia and its environs. The dance was originally danced by women from the six (6) villages that make up Isuofia town. Those women from the six villages came together in the 1950s and formed a dancing group known as *Okwurukwusike*. These villages are Umueze, Ozara, Isiaku, Ezioka, Okpoko and Akuru. They came together at a designated/secluded place known as Amaorji to learn and demonstrate the dance practically.

The *Okwurukwusike* Dance was organized and headed by twenty (20) selected women members from the six villages. During that time, *Okwurukwusike* was divided into three (3) groups, namely:

- ❖ *Okwurukwusike*
- ❖ *Egbebere*
- ❖ *Dimanu*

Furthermore, *Okwurukwusike* is meant for the elderly women. *Egbebere* is for middle – aged women who are daughters that are born and married in Isuofia respectively. This dance, then generated a lot of income for the group which they lend to their members that needed it at that time. They equally used the money they got from outings in building shops which they also gave out as rents to those that indicated interest. By the early 1960s, when Christianity came to Isuofia, the dance spread to other churches. As a result of this, when Bishop Arinze, the Archbishop of Onitsha then, visited St. Patrick Catholic Church Isuofia, on a pastoral visit where they were invited to perform; he converted and baptized many members of the group. Till today, those members who were baptized still retain their baptismal name.

However, some interview questions the researchers had with the respondents were stated respectively:

Interview with Roselyn Ezeanya

Researchers: When did *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group start?

Respondent: The dance started in the early 1950s

Researchers: Where is the venue for rehearsals?

Respondent: The venue is designated at Amaorji

Researchers: How many groups make up the dance?

Respondent: It is made up of three (3) groups

Researchers: Is there any hope for the continuity of this dance since most presently married women are set to urban centres?

Respondent: There is every hope and assurance of this expedient dance.

Researchers: How can it be possible?

Respondent: It can be possible through archiving (*Nchekwaba*) and generation transfer (*Nnyefe n'aka ndi na-etolite etolite*) of the dance group.

Researchers: Can this dance be archived since it is an indigenous rural dance group exclusively performed by women?

Respondent: Yes, there is hopeful assurance of this indigenous/cultural dance because of modern technological devices of safeguarding musical items in the museums, libraries and educational institutions. More so, these are the use of recording materials like discs, CDs, music studios to record, store and keep in secluded places for reference purposes.

Researchers: How can we ensure its generational transfer after the archiving?

Respondent: Once the dance is safeguarded in the recording materials and kept in the reference shelves, the possibility of transferring to up-coming generation is ensured. Traditionally, as an indigenous children and youth audience; watch, observe and carry it on to future ones coming after them because our dance is based on oral and practical demonstrations and performances. Furthermore, the dance carries the historical, economic and communities' traditions and values that cannot be phased out anyhow. As such, the dance is continuous to generations yet unborn.

Picture of the researchers with Roselyn Ezeanya

(Roselyn Ezeanya, Friday, 5th April 2024 4.00pm – 6.00pm. Ozara village, Isuofia)

Interview with Chinyere Onu

Researchers: Is this dance group important to the community?

Respondent: The dance is very important to the community and the entire society because it carries the social and cultural values as well as the historical and economic aspect of the town for future generations.

Researchers: How will the dance be passed on to them?

Respondent: We still have few young mothers that can carry and pass it on to the up-coming generations. Moreover, we hope to attract more young mothers that are yet to marry to the dance group since many are staying abroad with their spouses as abroad-financial members who do not know the dance techniques and its practical strategies for performances.

Researchers: What do you do with the money generated from your outings?

Respondent: At first, we lend the money to some of our members in need to help them with their businesses. Secondly, we use the money to build shops for renting to generate more revenue for the general welfare of the group.

Researchers: What other gain do the members of this group get for being a member?

Respondent: The dance group gives them sense of belonging, helps them socialize and relate with people thereby adapting to their conditions.

Picture of the researchers with the respondent Mrs. Chinyere Onu.
(Chinyere Onu; Saturday, 11th May 2024, 7.00am-10.00am. Umueze village, Isuofia).

Interview with Ebere Udensi

Researchers: In what language are the songs of *Okwukwusike* dance?

Respondent: The songs are in Igbo language with pure Isuofia dialect.

Researchers: How many songs does the musical group have?

Respondent: They are many

Researchers: Can you sing all of them?

Respondent: No, I can sing only the ones I know how to sing

Researchers: Do you have instruments for accompanying the dance?

Respondent: Yes, we have eight (8) local musical instruments as follows:

- (i) Ekwe – Wooden gong
- (ii) Oyo – Basket rattle
- (iii) Igba – Membrane drum
- (iv) Ichaka – Calabash rattle
- (v) Ubom/Alo – Big gong
- (vi) Ogene – Small gong
- (vii) Okpokolo – Wooden block
- (viii) Udu – Music pot

Researchers: How do you get the instruments in case of any replacement or repair?

Respondent: We buy them in the market. Some producers who make the instruments repair and supply some to us when there is need.

Researcher: Do you have costume for the dance group?

Respondent: Yes, they are dressed in red head gear and white lace blouse with beaded necklace of white and red seed-bead to match with the attire. The group's wrappers are designed in line with colors of black, red and white. The lines are the beautiful designs of *uli* (indigo), woven creatively and crafted in *Akwette* (Locally knitted) tradition textile technique cloth. It is certain that the group's costume is red, black and white that represents basic colors in Igbo land. We also have *Uzari* (Decorated Horse Tail) usually held by the group's patroness for signaling.

Picture of the researchers with the respondent Mrs. Ebere Udensi.
(Ebere Udensi, Friday, 7th June 2024; 5.00pm-7.00pm in Ezioko village, Isuofia, oral communication).

The dance group performing with their costume. Researchers are seen watching, observing, recording and expressing joy with the dance group.

Lyrical/textual and structural/musical examples of the songs discussed

From the above interviews with the owners and performers of the dance group. Some of the songs' lyrics and musical examples were briefly discussed. The topics were as follows.

Ugbo nd'egwu n'abia

Mbene Mbee

O di m egwu

Egwu okenu

Ndi nwoke nan di nwanyi amaghi akwukwu

Ugbo Ndi Egwu n'abia

This first song is calling on the audience's attention and interest to feed happily from the dance performance. It is called *Egwu Mputa* – Introductory Song.

Nonetheless, *Ume eze unu lee anya na iro*

Mbene Mbene song is portraying the importance of women in the cultural exhibition of events in the community. Thus, *mmamou umu nwanyi bu okaka*. The women masquerade is the best.

O di m egwu song is showcasing the women's lamentation and mourning when somebody dies...

I asked who died, the reply was that Peter is dead, which shows how women pass information across when something serious happens using their music.

Egwu Okenu exposes a man called Udensi and his artistic and aesthetic ingenuity in traditional music. In as much as the composers of oral music is unknown, Udensi has special qualities as regards our indigenous songs and an encourager to the dance group.

Ndi nwoke amaghi akwukwo

The song portrays that both the men and women couldn't record their music because they are not literate. However, the Bishop came and wrote to the governor about their welfare showing that there is need to be literate enough to learn and acquire knowledge.

Therefore, knowledge is power which can enable the process and possibility of recording, archiving and transferring of this music for its continuity.

The Musical Examples

Some of the musical, structural and lyrical examples are discussed as follows.

O DI M EGWU!

Na Mwute

Composed by Unknown
Arrangers: Osele Angelina .A
& Okechukwu Ifeoma .P

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

A no m n'u - no nu ka e - kwe n'a - gha O di m e - gwu! A -

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

no-kwa m n'u-no nu ka e-kwe n'a-gha O di m e-gwu! M ju-o o-nye nwu-ru a-si na Pi-ta

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

nwu-ru o - nwu di'e - gwu! M ju - o o - nye nwu-ru a - si na Pi - ta

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

nwu-ru o - nwu di'e - gwu! M wee tie o - ko - ko - ko... a - lu me - lu a nyi o n'u - lo e - gwu! M

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

tie o - ko - ko - ko... a - lu me - lu a nyi o n'U - mue ze

Ndiegwu (Response)

A no m n'u-no nu ka e-kwe n'a-

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IGBO

Anom na ulo nuka ekwe na aha odi megwu(2ce)

M juo onye nwuru asi na Peta nwuru onwu di egwu (2ce)

Ntie Okokoko, aru mere anyi nulo egwu

Ntie Okokoko, aru mere anyi na Umueze

ENGLISH

I was at home and heard ekwe blasting, it was awesome to me (2ce)

I asked, who died, the reply was that Peter died, I was thrown aback (2ce)

I screamed, okokokoo, disaster has falling on us in the dance the dance troupe

I screamed, okokokoko, disaster has visited us in Umueze

EGWU OKENU

Na Mwute

Composed by Unknown
Arrangers: Osele Angelina .A
& Okechukwu Ifeoma .P

Onyeisi egwu (Call) E-gwu n-ke a bu e-gwu O-ke - nu o! Aa-eeh! E-gwu n-ke a bu e-gwu O-ke -

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call) nu o! O-ke-nu nwa U-den - si o!

Ndiegwu (Response) E-gwu n-ke a bu e-gwu O-ke - nu o! Aa-eeh!

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

Ndiegwu (Response) E-gwu n-ke a bu e-gwu O-ke - nu o! O-ke - nu nwa U-den - si o!

IGBO

Egwu nkea bu egwu Okenu

A – eee, egwu nkea bu egwu Okenu,

Okenu nwa Udensi (2ce)

ENGLISH

The dance is okenu's dance

A – eee, this dance is Okenus dance, Okenu

from Udensi's lineage (2ce)

NDI NWOKE AMAGHI AKWUKWO...

Na Mwute

Composed by Unknown
Arrangers: Osele Angelina .A
& Okechukwu Ifeoma .P

The musical score consists of six systems, each with a 'Call' line (Onyeisi egwu) and a 'Response' line (Ndiegwu). The lyrics are in Igbo and are as follows:

- System 1: N-di nwo-ke a - ma-ghi a -kwu- kwo... N-di nwa-nyi a - ma-ghi a -kwu kwo!
- System 2: ma-na Bi sho - pu de-re a -kwu-kwo nye Go-va no a -nyi sia guo- lu a -nyi o!
- System 3: Go va-no a -nyi a - gu chaa a -kwu- kwo... nye I-gwe I- suo - fia sia guo- lu a -nyi o!
- System 4: I-he e-de-lu n'i-me a -kwu-kwo na m -ma-du n -cha bu o-fu n'i me a -nyi o! O-nye
- System 5: ru ba ru-sia n-di u - ka e -ji-de ya n-ga O ga-gha -ri-ba. Room n'a - bu e-nye-re ya O
- System 6: nyu si -si-cha a ya! N-di u-ka O kwa-nu e-zio-kwu-nu o! A - eeh!

The score ends with the text "N-di nwo-ke a" at the bottom right.

IGBO

*Ndi nwoke amaghi akwukwo
Ndi nwanyi amaghi akwukwo
Imana Bishop dere akwukwo nye Govano
ka oguoro anyi*

*Govano aguchaa akwukwo, nye Igwe
suofia ka oguoro anyi
Ihe ogutara na ime akwukwo bu na
bu ofu nime anyio
Onye ruba rusia ndi uka ejide ya nya
Gbagbariba*

Room na abo enyere ya Onyusichaa ya

*Ndi uka okwa ezi okwu, A-aaeh
A-aa-eh*

ENGLISH

Male are not literate
Females are not literate
Do you know that Bishop
wrote something and gave to the
Governor to read for us

Governor read and gave
to Igwe Isuofia to read for us
What he learnt from the Mmadu ncha
Message was that all of us are one
One works and at the end the
religious people and the person will
cage the person will run helter skater

The two rooms that were given to
the person was messed up
Religious people, is it the truth?

MBENE MBEE....

Na Obianuri

Composed by Unknown
Arrangers: Osele Angelina .A
& Okechukwu Ifeoma .P

Onyeisi egwu (Call) M-be- ne m - bee...

Ndiegwu (Response) N ga ne- ne a-gbo-gho n'a-gba e-gwu mo! N ga ne-

Onyeisi egwu (Call) U - nu fu - ru - mu nwa - nyi o!...

Ndiegwu (Response) ne a - gbo-gho n'o - gbo! M - ma-nwu u -

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

Ndiegwu (Response) mu- nwa - nyi bu m - ma-nwu o - ka - si O - nye no-du O ji a - nya ya hu - ru!

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

Ndiegwu (Response) A na m e - che-nu e-gwu m n - ga ne - ne a-gbo-gho n'o - gbo e!

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IGBO

Mbene mbee (Nga nene agbogho no ogbo egwu)

Mbene mbee (2ce)

Unu furu umu nwanyi o

Mmanwu nwanyi bu mmanwu okasi

Onye nodu, oji anya ya huru

Anam echere egwuo

Nganga nere agbogho na ogboe

ENGLISH

(let me go and watch a
damsel on the dance floor) (2ce)
Have you seen women o?

Our Masquerade is the best
Masquerade

When one sits, the person sees with
one's own eyes

I am waiting for the dance

Let me go and see a damsel on the
dance floor

O DI M EGWU!

Na Mwute

Composed by Unknown
Arrangers: Osele Angelina .A
& Okechukwu Ifeoma .P

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

A no m n'u - no nu ka e - kwe n'a - gha O di m e - gwu! A -

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

no-kwa m n'u-no nu ka e-kwe n'a-gha O di m e-gwu! M ju-o o-nye nwu-ru a-si na Pi-ta

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

nwu-ru o - nwu di'e - gwu! M ju - o o - nye nwu-ru a - si na Pi - ta

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

nwu-ru o-nwu di'e-gwu! M wee tie o - ko - ko - ko... a-lu me-lu a nyi o n'u lo e-gwu! M

Ndiegwu (Response)

Onyeisi egwu (Call)

tie o-ko-ko - ko... a-lu me-lu a nyi o n'U-mue ze

Ndiegwu (Response)

A no m n'u-no nu ka e-kwe n'a-

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IGBO

Anom na ulo nuka ekwe na aha odi megwu(2ce)

M juo onye nwuru asi na Peta nwuru onwu

di

egwu (2ce)

Ntie Okokoko, aru mere anyi nulo egwu

Ntie Okokoko, aru mere anyi na Umueze

ENGLISH

I was at home and heard ekwe blasting, it was awesome to me (2ce)

I asked, who died, the reply was that

Peter died, I was thrown aback (2ce)

I Screamed, okokokoo, disaster has falling on us in the dance the dance troupe

I screamed, okokoko, disaster has visited us in Umueze

NDI NWOKE AMAGHI AKWUKWO...

Na Mwute

Composed by Unknown
Arrangers: Osele Angelina .A
& Okechukwu Ifeoma .P

The musical score consists of six systems, each with a 'Call' line (Onyeisi egwu) and a 'Response' line (Ndiegwu). The lyrics are in Igbo and are as follows:

- System 1: N-di nwo-ke a - ma-ghi a-kwu- kwo... N-di nwa-nyi a - ma-ghi a-kwu kwo!
- System 2: ma-na Bi sho - pu de-re a -kwu-kwo nye Go-va no a-nyi sia guo- lu a-nyi o!
- System 3: Go va-no a-nyi a - gu chaa a-kwu- kwo... nye I-gwe I- suo - fia sia guo- lu a-nyi o!
- System 4: I-he e-de-lu n'i-me a-kwu-kwo na m - ma-du n-cha bu o-fu n'i me a-nyi o! O-nye
- System 5: ru ba ru-sia n-di u - ka e-ji-de ya n-ga O ga-gha - ri-ba. Room n'a - bu e-nye-re ya O
- System 6: nyu si-si-cha ya! N-di u-ka O kwa-nu e-zio-kwu-nu o! A - ech!

IGBO

*Ndi nwoke amaghi akwukwo
Ndi nwanyi amaghi akwukwo
Imana Bishop dere akwukwo nye Govano
ka oguoro anyi*

*Govano aguchaa akwukwo, nye Igwe
suofia ka oguoro anyi
Ihe ogutara na ime akwukwo bu na
bu ofu nime anyio
Onye ruba rusia ndi uka ejide ya nya
Gbagbariba*

Room na abo enyere ya Onyusichaa ya

*Ndi uka okwa ezi okwu, A-aaeh
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cage the person will run helter skater

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the person was messed up
Religious people, is it the truth?

Structurally, the music is in A major and in 4/4 time. The musical notes used are quaver, crotchet and minim with their equivalent rests. The instrument accompaniment is placed beside the great staff (left). More so, the music is in simple call and response form notable in African indigenous music and dance.

The Process of Ensuring Archiving and Generational Transfer of *Okwurukwusike* Dance Group

From the interviews held by the researchers of the study, there is every need to clarify the following

- ❖ How generational transfer can be ensured and/or achieved after the archiving.
- ❖ The process of archiving and generational transfer of indigenous resources including music.
- ❖ Identify the form of archiving that is being proposed as regards the study and the nature of the generational transfer.
- ❖ Situating the study in the context of other studies and arguments on the challenges of archiving indigenous music/dance.
- ❖ What has been proposed by colonial scholars on the issue of archiving indigenous music/dance for generational transfer to be possible?

In other to ensure generational transfer after the archiving, first, there is need to ensure the systematic process of documenting and preserving the dance group's performance. As seen, the due process and strategy of archiving should be followed duly such as recording and storage of the dance appropriately. Like keeping it in the museum, CDs, discs, libraries, departmental institutions that need it for knowledge acquisition and generational transfer. Olodale, Talabi and Okunade (2020) inferred that:

It is now common knowledge that functional framework for documentation and intellectual frameworks. The functionality and constant appraisal of such a framework thus valorizes documentation practices and archiving as institutions – where peoples' social, cultural and economic realities are critically engaged and negotiated. However, the underpinning idea of documentation and archiving is solely not about storing information of documents, rather, it is more about critical processing of the claims that archival information embodies (pp. 178-79)

From the above statement, it is clarified that once the data is stored or kept appropriately, the information will be easier to pass from generation to generation either orally, practically and/or educationally. However, there are other processes of archiving indigenous resources, including music for generational transfer. Nonetheless, archiving of indigenous resources has been in existence since the age's past. Aluede (2020) affirms that.

The need to preserve musical instruments, audio/visual files and documents has always been there since human existence. Although this has been perfunctorily done in the past, there is an ever-growing need for proper documentation and archiving. This need is unequivocally supported by the UNESCO Convention for the safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, article two (2) defines materials belonging to Intangible Cultural Heritage domains to include: oral traditions and expressions, including language as a vehicle of intangible cultural heritage, performing arts, social practices, rituals and festive events; knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe and traditional craftsmanship (p. 112)

The above statement ensures proper process of documentation, archiving and generational transfer proposed for this indigenous dance resources of *Okwurukwusike* group. As such, its continuity is ensured. Looking at the above discussions, the study can be situated in the context of other studies and arguments on the challenges of archiving this indigenous music of *Okwurukwusike*.

In as much as recording, documenting, archiving and generational transfer of this study is concerned, there will be some challenges awaiting it as indigenous dance group performance of Igbo land. Oladele, Talabi and Okunade (2020) postulated that,

This is the basic of Schwartz and Cook's argument that remembering (or recreating) the past through historical research in archival records is not simply the retrieval of stored information, but putting together of a claim above past states of affairs by means of a framework of shared cultural understanding. The performativity of claims about the past and its accrued social, political and economic potential for the future according to economic anthropologists, like Guyer, does not only situate archives as place of political and economic negotiation, but also as a site of power. This is simply because archives are about choice (of what to keep) and access (to in-group users) (p. 79).

Likewise, Aluede (2020) affirmed that.

It will be very misleading to think that it is the sole duty of the government to preserve the musical culture of her people. All hands are expected to be on deck in carrying out such an exercise because the people come first before the government and while the eye of the government cannot be everywhere, individual initiatives could be bought over by the government when such commitments are observed and beside nothing stops individuals from having personal collections (p. 112).

Therefore, the challenges of access towards archiving indigenous dance for generational transfer involves the individuals, groups, community and the entire society because they all come from a particular cultural area. Obiegbulem and Nwankpa (2020) observed that, "The challenge of archiving and documentation in Nigeria is the tendency to access the originality of these materials as long as life exist" (p. 66).

To this effect, there is serious need to create awareness on the documentation and archiving of our indigenous music like *Okwurukwusike* among others which will help our future generations. As such, it will create room for traditions' generational transfer. Dance as serious part of African culture plays importance and indigenous role in the transmission of our cultural values.

Ntorem (2019) affirmed that,

It is apparent that our culture must form the basis on which any other practice should be built. Okafor and Emeka defined culture as "all knowledge, beliefs customs, values, ideas and skills available in a society or societies and by which the society can be compared to or differentiated" from the fact that traditional dances carry some of the community's cultural practices, one outstanding thing is that it showcases the occupation of the community which could be noticeable through some of the dance steps and the traditional musical instruments used in accompanying the dance (p. 310).

The statement agrees with what our colonial scholars based on, that our indigenous dance or music can be recorded, documented, archived and transmitted to future generation for use. This can be achieved through the help of modern technological devices like CDs, Monographs, magazines, flash drives, discs which can also be stored in the museums, archives, libraries and event centres. As a matter of fact, the up-coming women of Izuofia and other communities will be attracted to continue the dance of *Okwurukwusike* among others using creative attribute and contributions of our colonial and post-colonial scholars. Vidal (2012) inferred that, "trained in European musical institutions and inculcated in the value system of their various ethnic cultures, Nigerian composers of art or serious music exhibit the European value of individualism in their creative works, a value that led to stylistic diversities in their creative expressions spiced with ethnic characteristic" (p. 6).

The above statement showcases the use of creative ideas and knowledge of our ancestors, post and present in documenting and archiving our indigenous dances/music for positive generational transfer.

Reasons for Documenting and Archiving of this Important Indigenous Dance Group for Generational Transfer.

Dance at large and indigenous dance group – like *Okwurukwusike* is very vital in our communities. Onwuekwe (2019) affirmed that, "Dance in Nigeria is held in high esteem since it keeps on occurring in different activities that cut across the rites of passage from birth to death" (p. 272). The attribute of a dance attracts and sustains the interest of the audience.

Ntrem (2019) asserted that:

Dance which deals with the rhythmic movement of the human body in time and space is an art form usually appreciated by individuals/groups of people. This is because the sounds produced by various musical instruments, the beautiful costumes worn by dancers, the paintings on the bodies of the dancers, the bracelets, hairdos and various dance steps showcased by the dancers are their creative works. All of these are so captivating and brings out the best in the audience in terms of inculcating good sense of appreciating beautiful things (p. 312).

Therefore, the music of *Okwurukwusike* dance group should be documented and archived for generational transfers for the following reasons.

- As a carrier and vehicle that transmits the community's ethical, historical, social and cultural values and heritage from generation to generation. Okafor (2005) stated that "they encourage sensibility by serving as cultural vehicle for encouraging teamwork (p. 82).
- Instruments of dance groups give awareness for ethnical recognition, exposure and identification.
- Dances encourage the continuous use of and aesthetic exposure of our indigenous musical instruments to the entire globe.
- Economically, the members are financially boosted from their monetary benefits.
- It gives recognition and exposure to the women in the rural areas.
- It protects and preserves a community's cultural heritage for continuity. Abdullahi and Ayoade (2020) ascertained that, "Music documentation is a form of preservation. Documenting traditional music is widely discussed as a way of protecting and preserving a people's cultural heritage (p. 51).
- It enhances socio-cultural relationship among individuals as they feature in festival activities. Nwamara (2023) posited that, "such festivals and feasts provide awareness for age groups and other classified groups to meet and build or strengthen effective and lasting friendship" (p. 24).
- Its documentation and archiving will prevent the music from total extinction.
- It builds an individual's firmness and growth in maturity for adoptability.
- Indigenous dance group creates opportunity for integrity, cultural identification and ethical recognition during music/dance carnivals.
- Costumes and uniform of dance groups give members a sense of belonging and happiness.
- Dance groups serve as generational resource materials for indigenous music education, through articulated bodily movements.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Music/dance is a powerful instrument of change for positive emotional inducement in the heart of every living soul. As such, *Okwurukwusike* as the name implies is a teachable aspect of dance/musical performance that carries the lyrics and demonstration attributes for the welfare of the women in particular, the community and the entire world of music at large. It gives the members a sense of boldness among fellow women folk wherever they are. More so, the spirit of oneness in indigenous dance and its growth/development is ensured for future usage because our indigenous dance is communally owned and performed by its community.

The researchers, therefore, recommend that sponsorships from individuals, groups, voluntary agencies, community and the government be attracted for more exposure. The documentation and archiving should be encouraged through the modern use of digital recording as well. The dance group should be recognized and exposed to perform at national and international events, and cultural carnival to boost our indigenous dance and its musical instruments. Policy makers should include such traditional studies in the educational curriculum. This will help in exposing our traditional dance and general musical activities for global acknowledge and recognition. More so, some important cultural dances in our traditional settings exist orally which may be forgotten unless they are documented and archived in journals, monographs, discs, CDs, flash drives or any digital system for generational transfer.

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Personal Interview/Communication

1. Sunday Osele: Saturday, 4th May 2024. 8 am - 10.30 am, Umueze Village, Isuofia
2. Okafor, Fidelis: Saturday, 7th June 2024, 2:00pm - 3.45pm. Ezioka Village Isuofia.
3. Roselyn Ezeanya: Friday, 5th April 2024, 4:00pm - 6:00pm. Ozara Village Isuofia.
4. Onu, Chinyere: Saturday, 11th May 2024, 7:00am - 10:00am. Umueze Village Isuofia.
5. Udensi, Ebere: Friday, 7th June 2024 5:00pm - 7:00pm